

Systematic Review Protocol

Systematic Review Protocol: Efficacy of Pharmacological and Non-Pharmacological Interventions in the Prophylaxis of Cluster Headache

1. Background and Rationale

Cluster headache (CH) is a highly disabling primary headache disorder characterized by severe unilateral pain, autonomic symptoms, and a circadian pattern of attacks. Effective prophylactic strategies are essential to reduce attack frequency, severity, and duration, thereby improving patients' quality of life. Pharmacological treatments, such as verapamil, lithium, and corticosteroids, have been widely used, while neuromodulation techniques, including vagus nerve stimulation and sphenopalatine ganglion stimulation, represent emerging alternatives. Recent studies have expanded the evidence base for CH prophylaxis, but the comparative effectiveness of these interventions remains uncertain. This systematic review aims to synthesize the latest evidence and provide guidance for clinical decision-making.

2. Objectives

To evaluate the effectiveness of pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions in the prophylaxis of cluster headache, considering factors such as attack frequency, duration, intensity, need for abortive medication, and quality of life improvements.

3. Eligibility Criteria

- Population: Adults (aged >18 years) diagnosed with cluster headache, including those with chronic cluster headache (duration >3 months) and refractory cases.
- Interventions: Pharmacological (verapamil, lithium, corticosteroids, galcanezumab) and non-pharmacological (vagus nerve stimulation, sphenopalatine ganglion stimulation) prophylactic treatments.

- Comparators: Studies without explicit comparators will be included.
- Study Design: Randomized and non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, and case-control studies.
- Outcomes: Reduction in attack frequency, duration, intensity, use of abortive medications, and quality of life measures.

4. Methods

- Search Strategy: A comprehensive search will be conducted in databases including Embase, MEDLINE, and PubMed. Only studies published in English will be considered.
- Study Selection: Two independent reviewers will screen studies based on predefined eligibility criteria, resolving disagreements through discussion.
- Data Extraction: Data will be extracted independently by two reviewers and discrepancies resolved through consensus.
- Risk of Bias Assessment: The Cochrane RoB-2 tool, Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, and ROBINS-I will be used to assess the risk of bias.
- Certainty of Evidence: A narrative synthesis approach will be used, considering study design, risk of bias, and consistency of results.

5. Data Synthesis

- The PRISMA flowchart will be used to document study selection.
- Standardized mean differences will be used to synthesize quantitative data.
- A qualitative synthesis will be performed for non-comparable outcomes.

6. Registration and Dissemination

This protocol is registered in PROSPERO (CRD420251012089). The full protocol and findings will be made publicly available via Zenodo and submitted for peer-reviewed publication.

7. Funding and Conflict of Interest

This review is conducted without external funding. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

8. Review Timeline

- Start date: 16 March 2025
- Expected completion: 16 April 2025